

Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings

Deliverable D.5.6 Report on the contribution to standardisation and standardisation road map

Deliverable Information

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¹ PU = PUBLIC fully open ((warning) automatically posted online on the Project Results platforms)
SEN = Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
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Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings

Project Profile

Programme	Horizon Europe
Call	HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01-23: Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials (RIA)
Number	101091464
Acronym	BIO-SUSHY
Name	Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings
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Duration	48 months
Type of action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
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Project Coordinator	MATERIA NOVA

Document History

Version	Date	Entity	Remarks
V1	14/11/2023	UNE	Draft shared with partners
V2	01/12/2023	UNE	Update with partners' feedback
V3	11/12/2023	UNE	Final version

Publishable Summary

The deliverable D5.6 is produced in the context of BIO-SUSHY-WP5, **Task 5.4 – Standardisation activities**, in particular *subtask 5.4.2 – Contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation developments*. D5.6 “Report on the contribution to standardisation and standardisation road map” will collect the actions performed for the contribution to standardisation from BIO-SUSHY and the results obtained. The contribution to standardisation seeks to transfer selected results of BIO-SUSHY to standards (EN/CLC/ISO/IEC). D5.6 will end up with D5.8 that shall be delivered at M48; however, it is considered that a first version of the document defining a strategy is needed for a successful contribution to standardisation.

The transfer of the results of BIO-SUSHY to standards that are widely recognized by the industry and that are developed in a system external to the Consortium will ease the market uptake of these results and their impact beyond the duration of the project. Additionally, the standardisation system is used as a targeted dissemination channel towards the stakeholders represented in the standardisation committees.

D5.6 is based on the conclusions of D5.5 “Report on the standardisation landscape and applicable standards” that included the information on the relevant existing and ongoing standards and the relevant standardisation technical committees to facilitate the use of existing knowledge and the compatibility and the interoperability of the results.

The Spanish Association for Standardisation (UNE), as a National Standardisation Body (NSB), member of CEN-CENELEC and ISO-IEC, is a partner of BIO-SUSHY who will provide support regarding the standardisation tasks included in the project (WP5 “Measures to maximise impact”).

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
EN	European Standard
ISO	International Organization for Standardisation; International Standard
UNE	Spanish Association for Standardisation
NSB	National Standardisation Body
SC	Subcommittee
TC	Technical Committee

1. Scope

This first version of D5.6 “Report on the contribution to standardisation and standardisation road map” defines a strategy for the contribution to standardisation from BIO-SUSHY. It includes the steps towards a successful contribution to standardisation, the actions for its implementation and a tentative schedule.

It will be updated with the progress of the different actions and their outcomes, resulting in an ultimate version of D5.8 at M48.

The schedule of the actions described in this document is open to changes according to the progress of the project and the standardisation landscape.

2. Definition of the strategy

The contribution to standardisation of BIO-SUSHY is based on the interaction with the relevant Standardisation Technical Committees and on the initiation of a standardisation process. The strategy comprises the actions represented in the next figure (Fig.1) and the different steps are explained below:

Figure 1 – Strategy for the contribution to standardisation of BIO-SUSHY.

2.1. First contact with the standardisation technical committees

Commenté [1]: Something wrong with the header on this page.

The objective of this first contact is to raise awareness about BIO-SUSHY among the relevant standardisation committees and to ease subsequent contacts. Different categories of stakeholders at the European/International levels are present in these committees, so the standardisation system is used as a targeted dissemination channel. Feedback will be asked to gather any views, opinions or advise about the project and the standardisation possibilities or needs. Additionally, these first contacts will be useful to determine the best path toward the initiation of a standardisation process, moreover, this first step will ease future contacts if this process is launched within a standardisation committee.

2.2. Subsequent interaction with the standardisation technical committees

Different relationships can be established with the relevant CEN/CENELEC, ISO/IEC technical committees. Two factors determine the most suitable interactions: the impact/relevance of the standardisation works of the standardisation committees and the feasibility of initiating a standardisation process within a standardisation committee (versus initiating the standardisation process within a standardisation workshop, details are given below). The ways of interaction of the project with the standardisation committees include:

1. **Follow-up the activity of the relevant standardisation committees.** This allows to detect the initiation of standardisation works that can be relevant for BIO-SUSHY and the progress of significant existing under-development standards. This is achievable through a periodical monitoring of the standardisation activity.
2. **Further contact with the standardisation committees to update the progress of BIO-SUSHY.** This is achievable by delivering reports, by attending relevant technical committees' meetings or by joint events. On the one hand, this action contributes to further dissemination of the project and can guide the initiation of the standardisation process, on the other hand, this further contact is mandatory towards the standardisation committees directly covering (if it were the case) the subject that will be promoted by BIO-SUSHY to undergo a standardisation process.
3. **The participation of one or more BIO-SUSHY partners in the standardisation technical committees.** Standardisation is an open activity and all interested parties may participate in the technical committees through the designation of their National Standardisation Body. This option allows for a deeper follow-up of the activity of a standardisation committee and is valuable if the standardisation process is initiated within the standardisation committee.

4. **The establishment of a formal liaison of BIO-SUSHY with the standardisation committees.** It is recommended only when the work of the standardisation committee is closely linked with the main goals of the project and a direct technical contribution from the project is expected. The figure of project liaison is recognized in CEN/CENELEC, but it is not very effective in ISO/IEC, this shall be taken into account.

2.3. Standardisation process

The main objective of the standardisation activities in BIO-SUSHY is to facilitate the market acceptance of the results by transferring these results and findings to standards that have a wide recognition in the market. With the collaboration of the relevant partners, the feasible results to go through a standardisation process will be identified. Different options to contribute to standardisation shall be considered depending on the kind of the results (nature, availability and IPR) and the standardisation context (existence of closely related standards and reactions of the standardisation committees):

1. **Development of a new standard within a standardisation workshop.** A standardisation workshop is a group of entities with a common interest in developing a standard about a specific issue. It is the equivalent figure to the standardisation committee, but the number of participants is typically smaller and the working procedures are faster and more flexible. A standardisation workshop is created when there is a need to develop a precise standard in an innovative field that is not covered by the existing standardisation committees or when these committees are not interested in developing such standard (e.g., it does not fit their work programme). If the subject is close to the field covered by a standardisation committee, the latter shall be informed and shall allow for the launching of the standardisation workshop.

Considering that the standardisation workshop option is interesting for BIO-SUSHY mainly in the European environment, the standardisation workshop will be named herein after as CEN Workshop or CENELEC Workshop. The standard produced by a CEN/CENELEC Workshop is called the CEN Workshop Agreement or CENELEC Workshop Agreement, known as CWA. The nature and timeline for the development of CWAs are very suitable for the framework of the R&I projects.

2. **Standardisation within a standardisation committee.** It may be interesting or needed that the results of BIO-SUSHY to go through the standardisation process are standardised within a standardisation committee. The possible scenarios are:
 - a. *Development of a new standard within a standardisation committee.* When there is a result of BIO-SUSHY to be promoted to a standard in a field covered by a standardisation committee and such committee decides to include this development

in its work programme. The resulting standard would have the support of the standardisation committee, but the work shall be adapted to the internal timeline of such standardisation committee and could go beyond the timeframe of the project.

- b. *Contribute to an on-going standard.* As a consequence of the monitoring of the standardisation landscape, it may be found that the results of BIO-SUSHY are covered by an ongoing standard but that these results do not fit the current draft of the standard. Gaps in standards may be found in both, standards that are being developed from a new initiative, and standards already published that are going under a review process towards a new version.
- c. *Request the modification of a standard that is not under development or review.* The gap may also be found in published standards that are not under any work within the standardisation committee. In this case, a fully justified modification request can be made to the standardisation committee.
- d. *Outline of a future standard.* Only when there is no clear view of a full roadmap for the contribution to standardisation (like lack of agreement within the Consortium or lack of the expected results).

3. Implementation

The actions and approach to be performed for the implementation of each of the steps of the strategy described in clause 3 are detailed here below.

3.1. First contact with the standardisation technical committees

For the implementation of the actions described in 2.1 the relevance of the standardisation committees identified in D5.5 shall be considered. It shall be noticed that among the topics identified in D5.5, BIO-SUSHY particularly targets to develop novel bio-based durable water and oil repellent coatings (sol-gel and powder), which will be validated in 3 target markets: textile, food packaging and packaging for cosmetic applications. To meet these objectives, the development will be based on 3 pillars, R&I (Research and Innovation) coating development, supported by computational modelling of coating performances, toxicity assessment and by SSbD (Safe and Sustainable-by-Design) methodology to ensure safety and environmental performances, with a decrease by 25 % of environmental impact.

For the rest of the topics identified in D5.5, no relevant innovation is expected in the project, their consideration is useful in terms of compatibility of the developments of the project. Table 1 includes the topics and standardisation committees (European and International) identified in D5.5 and the standardisation committees proposed for get in contact with the objectives described in 2.1:

Table 1 – Standardisation committees relevant for further standardisation activities.

Subject	Technical committee	To be contacted
Coatings	ISO/TC 35 – Paints and varnishes	Yes
	ISO/TC 35/SC 15 – Protective coatings: concrete surface preparation and coating application	
	ISO/TC 35/SC 9/WG 16 – Coating powders	
	CEN/TC 139 – Paints and varnishes	
Raw materials	ISO/TC 61 – Plastics	Yes
	ISO/TC 61/ SC 5 – Physical - Chemical properties	
	ISO/TC 61/ SC 9 – Thermoplastic materials	
	CEN/ TC 411 – Bio-based products	
Coating characterization	ISO/TC 35 – Paints and varnishes	No
	CEN/TC 139 – Paints and varnishes	
	ISO/TC 6 – Paper, board and pulps	
	CEN/TC 172 – Pulp, paper and board	
Case studies	ISO/TC 38 – Textiles	Yes
	CEN/TC 248 – Textiles and textile products	
	CEN/TC 194 – Utensil in contact with food	
	ISO/TC 217 – Cosmetics	
	CEN/TC 329 – Cosmetics	
Nanosafety issues	ISO/TC 229 – Nanotechnologies	No

	CEN/TC 352 – Nanotechnologies	
Toxicity evaluation	ISO/TC 146 – Air quality	No
	CEN/TC 264 – Air quality	
	ISO/TC 61 – Plastics	Yes
	CEN/TC 249 – Plastics	
	ISO/TC 219 – Floor coverings	
	CEN/TC 134 – Resilient and textile floor coverings	
	ISO/TC 35 – Paints and varnishes	
	CEN/TC 139 – Paints and varnishes	
	ISO/TC 147 – Water quality	No
	CEN/TC 248 – Textile and textile products	Yes
Computational tools	ISO/IEC JTC 1 – Information technology	No
	ISO/TC 46 – Information and documentation	
	ISO/TC 171 – Document management application	
	ISO/TC 184 – Automation systems and integration	
	CEN/CLC JTC 21 – Artificial intelligence	
Life cycle	ISO/TC 207 – Environmental management	No

UNE will contact the Secretary/Convenor of each selected standardisation committee and subcommittee (Contact list in the **Annexe A** and e-mail model in the **Annexe B**). The support of the Coordinator/Partners of BIO-SUSHY will be needed to summarize the relevant progress and validate the information to disseminate, avoiding any confidential content (**Annexe C**).

These first contacts are foreseen between M10 and M15.

3.2. Subsequent interaction with the standardisation technical committees

The implementation of the actions described in 2.2 starts with the monitoring of the work of the standardisation committees identified in D5.5. This surveillance will also include the analysis of European standardisation workshops. The monitoring of the relevant standardisation activity will be continuous during the duration of BIO-SUSHY but tentative formal dates can be set:

- M15 (after the first contact with the standardisation committees)
- M24 (to be aligned with the needs of the standardisation process described in 2.3)
- M36 (to be aligned with the needs of the standardisation process described in 2.3)

The standardisation committees included in Table 1 will be updated with the relevant progress in BIO-SUSHY. This will be done by updating the report/information provided in the first contacts and, at the same time, keeping open the possibility of having a face-to-face interaction (e.g. attending to a meeting of the standardisation committee if feasible). The programming of these updates depends on the reactions to the first contacts and on when the relevant outcomes of BIO-SUSHY are delivered.

In any case, the support of the partners for the presentations, i.e., their preparation and the actual presentation to the committee – both with UNE, will be needed to summarize the relevant progress and validate the information to disseminate avoiding any confidential content.

Further interaction with the standardisation committees (participation of members of BIO-SUSHY in these committees and the consideration of a liaison project) will be determined according to the outcomes of the described communications and the approach of the standardisation process described in 2.3.

3.3. Standardisation process

Based on the identification of standardisable results, in the standardisation landscape at the moment (result of the interaction with the standardisation committees and the monitoring of their standardisation works) and the progress of the project, the most suitable roadmap among the options described in 2.3 will be selected and conducted.

A dedicated standardisation session to work on the identification of the standardisable results and the election of the roadmap is foreseen in BIO-SUSHY. This session could take place during a physical or online project meeting. A tentative date for this standardisation session is M20/M24.

The standardisation process is considered very valuable for the market uptake of the results of BIO-SUSHY and for the project's impact beyond the financing period. The decisions taken, the actions

performed, and the results obtained will be properly presented as part of D5.8 in Month 48 (December 2028).

3.4. Summary of the implementation

The summary of the tentative dates and the responsible for the actions is included in the next table 2:

Table 2 – Summary of the actions in the strategy towards a contribution to standardisation.

Action	Responsible	Month
First contacts with the standardisation committees in Table 1	UNE (content provided by the Coordinator)	M10 - M15
Updates on the standardisation landscape	UNE	Continuous but formally at M15 M24 M36
Provision of updated report/information to the standardisation committees identified in Table 1	UNE (content provided by the Coordinator)	M24 M30 Whenever it is demanded
Face to face interaction with the relevant standardisation committees	UNE and Coordinator/Partners	When relevant
Dedicated standardisation session	UNE	M20/M24
Standardisation process	UNE and Coordinator/Partners	M30 - M48

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ANNEX A: List of Secretaries of the selected standardization committees

Technical committee	Programme Manager / Secretary contact
ISO/TC 35 – Paints and varnishes	Annemieke Venemans / NEN
CEN/TC 139 – Paints and varnishes	Alessia Gaetani / DIN
ISO/TC 61 – Plastics	Jiandong Wang / SAC
CEN/TC 249 – Plastics	Alessia Gaetani / SIS
CEN/TC 411 – Bio-based products	Alessia Gaetani / NEN
ISO/TC 38 – Textiles	Yong Xu / SAC
CEN/TC 248 – Textiles and textile products	Dalier Claire / BSI
CEN/TC 194 – Utensil in contact with food	Christina Thorngreen /AFNOR
ISO/TC 217 – Cosmetics	Elham Ghasemi / INSO
CEN/TC 329 – Cosmetics	Christina Thorngreen / DIN
ISO/TC 219 – Floor coverings	Karin Eufinger / NBN
CEN/TC 134 – Resilient and textile floor coverings	Pargana Nuno / NBN

*Contact details are omitted due to data protection issues.

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ANNEX B: Communication text

***The following text will be sent by email in a letter format (pdf file) to the secretariat of the TCs selected so that it will be easily disseminated among TC members.**

Dear Mr, Ms **XXX**

I'm addressing you on behalf of the Horizon Europe project **BIO-SUSHY** which aims to develop innovative coating solutions that will be designed to meet the policy ambition of the EU's chemical strategy for sustainability toward a toxic-free environment. BIO-SUSHY targets the development of novel bio-based durable water and oil repellent coatings (sol-gel and powder), which will be validated in 3 target markets: textile, food packaging and packaging for cosmetic applications. To meet the objectives, the development will be based on 3 pillars, R&I (Research and Innovation) coating development, supported by computational modelling of coating performances, toxicity assessment and by SSbD (Safe and Sustainable-by-Design) methodology to ensure safety and environmental performances, with a decrease by 25 % of environmental impact.

As part of this project, **UNE (the Spanish standardisation body)** representing CEN/CENELEC in BIO-SUSHY is responsible for specific standardisation activities, which include:

- Ensure compatibility with existing technologies by identifying relevant existing standards.
- Maximize dissemination to proper stakeholders by addressing the relevant standardisation technical committees.
- Contribute with the findings and knowledge generated during the project to the development of standardisation in the field.

Paragraph linking the project with the TC

Also, for your information, other ISO and CLC TCs will be also contacted with this information.

The objective of this contact is twofold: firstly, to raise awareness about the project within this TC and gather feedback, suggestions, questions, or comments. Secondly, it is anticipated that in the second half of the project, it will contribute to standardisation based on selected project results. Depending on several factors, such as the nature of these results and the standardisation landscape at the moment, this contribution to standardisation may be oriented to generating new pre-standards (Workshop Agreements) or to participating at TC level.

Please, find attached a brief summary containing the most relevant information about BIO-SUSHY (further detailed on the [webpage](#)). Feel free to circulate this information to your TC members or to anyone you consider potentially interested in the objectives and results of the project. Now the project is 1/3 progressed and we would be very grateful if you could give us feedback regarding the interest of this project for the activity of the TC. Additionally, any suggestion, question or comment related to the project would be very useful.

Therefore, I would appreciate it if we could receive feedback from the TC on these aspects before the **31st of January**:

- Would the TC be interested in the results of the project to contribute to future standardisation activities?

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- Would you be interested in further communication of the project, including, for example, a broader presentation of the project at one of your meetings?

If you find that additional information would be welcome, as well as other kinds of contact (a dedicated telco, attending to a TC, SC or WG meeting to explain the project, etc.) we would be pleased to address it.

Thank you in advance for your attention and looking forward to your reply.

Best regards,

Javier Idiago López

Member of BIO-SUSHY

The Spanish Association for Standardisation - UNE

Tel: +34 628 501 276

fidiago@une.org

ANNEX C: Project Summary

The cover page features a central logo with a stylized 'b' inside a green square, flanked by two decorative patterns of overlapping cubes. Below the logo, the text 'BIO-SUSHY' is written in a bold, green, sans-serif font. The title 'Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings' is centered below the logo. The page is divided into sections: '1. Introduction' and '2. Technical Objectives'. The introduction paragraph describes the project's scope and goals. The technical objectives section lists five key goals. At the bottom, there is a small logo of the European Union and a disclaimer text.

1. Introduction

BIO-SUSHY is an EU-Horizon project involving 14 stakeholders from research and technology developers (RTDs), small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), a university, and a national association. It is based on an interdisciplinary approach to achieving high-quality, durable, and sustainable composite coatings to replace polluting polyfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS).

The coating solutions will be developed under the Safe- and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) concept based on bio-based thermoplastic powder and hybrid sol-gel technologies. These types of durable water and oil-repellent coatings will cover various applications and sectors, such as textile, glass cosmetic, and food packaging.

2. Technical Objectives

- Development and validation of three PFAS-free innovative repellent organic and hybrid coatings obtained from bio-based thermoplastic powder and hybrid sol-gel technologies.
- Collection of existing (eco)toxicological and physicochemical data of existing coatings.
- Use of in silico models for physical and data-driven modelling.
- Development of a hub for data storage and exchange.
- Development of a Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) strategy and life cycle assessment (LCA) to determine economic and environmental impacts along the value chains.

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BIO-SUSHY

3. List of partners involved and Work Packages workflow

BIO-SUSHY COORDINATOR:
Materia Nova, Av. Nicolas Copernic 3, 7000 Mons, Belgium

MATERIA NOVA

Partners involved:

- Ceriglio Nazionale Istito Ricerca
- AcumenIST
- ecozema
- Institut Français de Recherche en Technologie
- ASA INNOVATION
- UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS
- WOOD K PLUS
- VERI
- RESOLL
- SIKEMIA
- ITENE
- ProtoQSAR
- UNE

The BIO-SUSHY project is broken down into 6 work packages, including:

1. aligning project specifications with internal and external framework conditions as well with social acceptance criteria,
2. development and validation of novel coatings,
3. data collection, curation, and modelling,
4. building a Safe- and Sustainability-by-Design Framework,
5. setting up and implementing a communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan,
6. providing the consortium with adequate tools for guaranteeing the time delivery of all results.

WP1 (ZSI): Specifications, Alignment & Social Acceptance (M01-M48)

WP2 (RESOLL): SsbD-driven R&I of three novel Coating Materials and Demonstration of Industrial Assay (M04-M45)

WP3 (TP9): Computational Tools for the SsbD of Coating Materials (M03-M48)

WP4 (ITENE): BIO-SUSHY SsbD Framework for PFAs-free coatings (M01-M48)

WP5 (AXIA): Measures to maximize impact (M01-M48)

WP6 (MAND): Scientific Coordination & Project Management (M01-M48)

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4. Results obtained up to date (October 2023)

- First promising results on thermoplastic-based formulations with polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) and polybutylene succinate (PBS) bioplastics, which have acted as good grease and water-repellence barriers on paper substrates.
- Synthesis of bio-based linkers.
- A PFAS-free coating solution applied on different textile fabrics showed hydrophobic properties. The washing resistance of the coating to laundry cycles is being investigated.
- Fully developed release flow cell technology for testing coatings for stability and toxicity.
- Developed and implemented data-driven workflows for the physical simulation of materials relevant to the BIO-SUSHY applications.
- The BIO-SUSHY registry and the Instance Maps are being introduced for data management and sharing within the project. The BIO-SUSHY registry enhances data findability and accessibility, while Instance Maps provide an organized structure for describing interlinking and dependencies of processes, material transformations, modelling and SSbD testing.
- An analysis of the standardization landscape concerning the relevant standards (ISO and EN) for the project has already been completed.

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5. Contact details

MATERIA NOVA (Project Coordinator)

 Av. Nicolas Copernic 3,
7000 Mons, Belgium

 +32 65 55 49 02

 info@bio-sushy.eu

 www.bio-sushy.eu

 [@BIO-SUSHY Project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/bio-sushy-project)

 [@BIO-SUSHY](https://twitter.com/BIO-SUSHY)

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